

A PEDAGOGICAL MODEL FOR EDUCATION STUDENTS IN MICROBIOLOGY AND PARASITOLOGY

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A Pedagogical Model for Education Students in Microbiology and Parasitology

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Abstract

COVID - 19 significantly caused impact in the academic performance of the students. Thus, this study was conducted to design a pedagogical model for the college Science Students with Microbiology and Parasitology in Flexible Learning Modality in selected Tertiary Education Institutions of Region 12. A Quantitative Evaluative Research Design was employed to provide a clear and concise overview of data patterns and distribution. A validated achievement test with the employment of KR20 used to evaluate the performance level of the respondents. An in-depth interview of the selected participants on their experiences in Flexible Learning Modality was also performed. Findings of the study showed that the performance levels of Students in the content areas and cognitive skills were less mastered and found to be significantly different. These implied that the students' performance levels across the content areas and cognitive skills needed improvement with pedagogical adjustment. Hence, the MERick pedagogical model proposed to enhance teachers' pedagogy in College Microbiology and Parasitology in Flexible Learning Modality.

Keywords: *content mastery, cognitive skills, pedagogical model, flexible learning modality, performance level*

Introduction

The spread of the COVID-19 virus was reported in Wuhan, China, last December of 2019 (Yang et al., 2020), and the pandemic was declared worldwide by the World Health Organization or WHO (Jebri, 2020). This urgent declaration significantly impacted the whole world, specifically its socioeconomic sectors, including the education sector, mainly caused higher institutions to implement the full online modality to reduce physical contamination. Reported by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization or UNESCO (2020) that in the middle of May 2020, students from higher education who stopped attending physical education are included in the 1.2 billion students from various levels who were also forced to stop the physical education across the globe due to COVID - 19 outbreak and shifted into online modality. Gewin (2020) emphasizes that discontinued physical education can cause various crises, such as students' low academic performance, particularly those in state universities and colleges.

The significant change caused by the virus in higher education is also observed by Basalia et al. (2020), in which students experienced new environmental changes, interaction with people, and education. With these changes, it caused the reinvention of practices to sustain educational delivery in higher institutions through flexible learning modality (Sufyan et al., 2020), including the adjustment of the appropriate teaching methods (Huang, 2020), how to induce the students' participation and engagement (Sunasee, 2020), and the use of the technology or different platforms in flexible learning delivery (Tigaa & Sonawane, 2020). They are considered online platforms as the most well-known instruments nowadays since the pandemic outbreak started (Reviandani, 2021).

However, despite these strategies, the online transfer of knowledge is more on theoretical content and dismisses hands-on activities on the theories and concepts because of the virus restrictions. Hence, the learning process does not achieve its target (Bedenlier et al., 2020).

In the Philippines, the country is behind in terms of quality of education, particularly in a science subject (Rogayan & Dollete, 2019). Unfortunately, COVID - 19 pandemic significantly affected the country's academic performance specifically science education. Balontong et al. (2022) conducted a study at Notre Dame of Midsayap College, Midsayap, Cotabato to determine the content mastery level in Microbiology and Parasitology during synchronous and asynchronous under COVID-19 pandemic. The findings of the study showed that the pretest and post-test mean scores of the respondents in asynchronous class do not increase that high and it means that there is no significant difference between the pretest and post-test mean scores of the respondents in asynchronous class. This can be concluded that students taking Microbiology and Parasitology subjects could learn more during synchronous class or with the guidance of the subject teacher.

De la Calle (2021) believed that despite the empirical findings from various reports and studies about the academic performance of the students due to global pandemic in the previous two years, still there is a need of an in-depth study. As mentioned by Bedenlier et al. (2020) that although there are reinventions made in education such as flexible learning modality, there is no guarantee that the objectives of the subjects are achieved because online delivery disengages students in some cognitive skills.

Thus, the present study aimed to determine the significant impacts of the pandemic to the local education sectors specifically in Mindanao Region 12. Specifically, to investigate further the academic performance level in the content mastery areas and cognitive skills of selected Students in Tertiary Education Institutions (TEIs) in Region 12. The study's findings were used to design a pedagogical model for college microbiology and parasitology for education students.

Research Questions

The study designed a Pedagogical Model in Microbiology and Parasitology for College Students. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the performance level of the respondents in the following content areas:
 - 1.1. general morphology of organism;
 - 1.2. infections and host resistance;
 - 1.3. microbial controls;
 - 1.4. transmission and pathogenesis; and
 - 1.5. communicable diseases involving different organ systems?
2. What is the performance level of the students in the following cognitive skills:
 - 2.1. knowledge;
 - 2.2. comprehension;
 - 2.3. applications; and
 - 2.4. analysis?
3. Is there a significant difference in the performance level of the respondents across the different content areas?
4. Is there a significant difference in the performance level of the respondents across the different cognitive skills?
5. What are the experiences of teachers and students in microbiology and parasitology in the flexible learning modality?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what pedagogical model can be designed?

Methodology

Research Design

The study was basically a Quantitative Evaluative Research Design (Creswell, 2018) since the study investigated a particular topic or activity through the measurement of variables in quantifiable terms. This idea was similarly described by Gay et al. (2009) that this type of research design relies on the collection and analysis of numerical data to describe, explain, predict, or control variables and phenomena of interest. In the study, the researcher evaluated the performance level of students using validated achievement test and was administered for those college students who have already finished college microbiology and parasitology.

Respondents

The problems of the study were quantitatively answered using the validated achievement test given to the 192 Bachelor in Science Education Students who just recently finished taking the Microbiology and Parasitology in selected Tertiary Education Institutions (TEIs) in Region 12. Due to ethical considerations, out of 192 respondents who took the test, only 20 participated in the Focus Group Discussions or FGDs and for the Key Informant Interviewees or KIIs only 10 who participated in the in-depth interview in the study. The FGD and in-depth interview of the participants provided qualitative data and supported the results of the current performance level of students in content areas and cognitive skills in College Microbiology and Parasitology.

Instruments

The study used a validated achievement test and evaluated the performance level on the content areas and cognitive skills of BSED – 3 Science Students in Microbiology and Parasitology specifically for the sub – problems 1 and 2 of the study. Hence, the development of the achievement test with 75 – items multiple choice was based on the specific content areas of the course such as General Morphology of Organism, Infections and Host Resistance, Microbial Controls, Transmission and Pathogenesis, and Communicable Diseases Involving Different Organ Systems while in the Cognitive Skills of the course focused on the Student’s Knowledge, Comprehension, and Application.

Items from each content area and cognitive skills were specified using the One – Way Table of Specification (TOS) to identify the achievement domains being measured and to ensure an equal representative sample of questions included in the test. According to Prescott (2011) that the questionnaire must be thoroughly validated in order to provide scientific interrogations towards the respondents. Further, validation allows the validity, reliability and the appropriateness of the items of the questionnaire to be used. Also, to check if the questions are within the parameters of the study purpose to avoid questions statements like rude, bias, and unfair to the respondents. This is to ensure ethical considerations in the study to protect the individual’s right and privacy. In achievement test validation, the researcher sought permission from the 3 Content Expert Validators. Content experts determined if a test is accurate, appropriate, and fair.

Procedure

The study followed simple steps in data gathering from the respondents and participants: Preparatory phase, Evaluation - Interview phase of the validated achievement test, and Retrieval / collection phase of the achievement test and transcription of the FGD and KII of the study.

In the preparatory phase. A notice to proceed was sought to the office of Commission of Higher Education in Region 12 (CHEDRO12) then afterwards selected Tertiary Education Institutions or TEIs' Presidents/Chancellors were asked permission for the study conduct in their respective institutions. The permission letter was addressed to the Presidents/chancellors thru vice president of the academic affairs. Once obtained the permission from school authorities, it was then forwarded to the Deans of the College of Teacher Education or CTE.

While seeking permissions, attached documents in the permission letter were the title of the study, objectives and statements of the problems, scopes and delimitation, validated achievement test and a copy of the informed consent for the FGD and KII. Also, thorough validations of the achievement test, and series of item analyses of the content experts, test administration were also part of the preparation in the study. Importantly, building rapport between researcher and respondents, and likewise researcher and participants were considered as part of the preparatory in the study.

With proper approach and communication before the actual study helped removed gap between the researcher and respondents-participants by introducing Researcher's name, and then knowing Teachers' real names, years in teaching, basic information concerning the Teacher's class schedule particularly when she or he teaches Microbiology and Parasitology, number of the enrolled Students of the subject, their year levels, and specific degrees in Science. Knowing the backgrounds of the respondents provide smooth delivery of the Researcher and Teacher transaction for the study development.

Third, once the rapport has been built between the Researcher and Teachers, agreement of the conduct schedule of the achievement test administration and in-depth interview followed and then the fourth step is that the Researcher provided an invitation letter to those qualified Students to take the test. Once the qualified Students understood the study's objectives and expressed their willingness to participate in the test, they were given the full information of the title, purpose of the study, scopes and delimitation, instrument, and their roles were emphasized. Further, the Researcher assured the confidentiality and the secrecy of the outcome of the test once collected / retrieved after the test administration.

Evaluation - Interview Phase of the Validated Achievement Test. The study had two sub-phases employed. First, respondent's administration of the validated achievement test to the 192 respondents in selected TEIs of Region 12. In the test administration, Students who have just recently taken Microbiology and Parasitology with a BSED-Science degree were the main respondents in the study. During the test administration, the Researcher explained thoroughly the General rules in taking the test such as gadgets are not allowed while having the test, talking with seatmates, no cheating, going in and out during the test, and etc. Includes also the time allotted for the test and hence finished or unfinished they will pass the achievement test in front. After they have taken the test, the researcher informs or invites those respondents who showed willingness and signed the informed consent as participants in the Focus Group Discussions or FGDs.

Therefore, those respondents who did not sign the informed consent were excluded as participants in the study. The researcher made sure that those participants in the FGD understood the entire process of the group discussions. For instance, the FGD objectives, their significant roles as participants, and the usefulness of the data gathered from them. The FGD started in a designated closed - room when all participants were settled and understood the informed consent contents. At the end of the FGD, the researcher made sure that whatever information being shared or divulged in the discussions, all is kept / treated as confidential and only used for the purpose of the study. On one hand, the participants in the Key Informant Interview or KII were those Science teachers who taught Microbiology and Parasitology in selected TEIs. The KII participants were treated as those FGD participants in the study. Teacher's interview was conducted while the student's evaluation was ongoing.

Retrieval / Collection Phase of the Achievement Test and Transcription of the FGD and KII of the Study. The submission for the retrieval of the achievement test started from the last Respondent seated in the last chair going to the first Respondent seated in the first chair by column. They were encouraged to ask for further clarification if there were confusing items. A one-hour test was given to the Respondents and then followed the retrieval of the achievement test. Checking of the achievement test followed. Results of achievement tests were interpreted using the mean, percentage, and ANOVA to produce plausible conclusions of the study.

On one hand, the retrieved / transcribed in-depth interviews of the Teachers and the Students were analyzed and interpreted following the steps of Colaizzi (1978): read and re-read each transcript in order to obtain a general sense about the whole content. It ensured that all important highlights of the statements from the whole conversations were heard, recorded, and extracted carefully. For each transcript, significant statements that pertained to the phenomenon are extracted where the meanings are formulated from these significant statements. The formulated meanings are arranged into cluster themes which evolved into emergent themes. Clustering is very important in doing a qualitative approach of investigation. During the duration of the conversation between the interviewee might be similar or synonymous from the previous answers of the previous questions. Therefore, redundancy of the responses might occur during the interview. In this case, clustering of the homogeneous and heterogeneous statements is significant.

The findings are integrated into an exhaustive description of the lived experience, fundamental structure of the phenomenon is described, and lastly the validation of findings from the participants. As a researcher in the study, you should inform the respondents of the study. These emergent themes are all determining factors in the experiences of the Teachers and Students under the flexible learning modality of the results of the interview.

The transcription of the FGD and KII provided qualitative data and answered the 5th problem of the study on Students and Teachers' experiences in Microbiology and Parasitology in Flexible Learning Modality. Hence, it supported and answered the 6th problem which is the appropriate design of pedagogical model for online modality.

Ethical Consideration

It is very important that the study respects the right and privacy of the participants. Hence, of the entire duration of the study, ethical considerations were observed such as the informed consent's objective, confidentiality or anonymity, communication of the study is considered.

The objectives of the study were clearly stated including the statement of the problems, scope and delimitation, and the significance of the study to the target TEIs and to their Teachers and Students. Participants were humbly asked to take part in a research study. Before they decide to participate in this study, it is important that they understand why the research was being done and what it will involve. Researcher encouraged them to ask if there was anything that was not clear or if they need more information. Also, the researcher described the objectives of the experiences of teachers and students in Microbiology and Parasitology in the flexible learning Modality.

Confidentiality or anonymity of the Respondents. By not divulging any demographic profiles of all the Respondents such as their real names, and home addresses. The participants' responses to this study considered anonymous. Hence, they were humbly instructed not to include any identifying information. Every effort was made by the researcher to preserve the confidentiality including the following:

Assigning code names/numbers for participants used on all research notes and documents, Keeping notes, interview transcriptions, and any other identifying participant information in a locked file cabinet in the personal possession of the researcher, and Participant data are kept confidential except in cases where the researcher is legally obligated to report specific incidents. These incidents include, but may not be limited to, incidents of abuse and suicide risk.

Communication of the study. Researcher is never allowed to share the information gathered from the participants except obtained the permission or approval from the Targeted TEIs and the Respondents. The researcher is fully aware of the Republic Act 10173 - Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Results

This section shows the overview of the presentation of key findings such as the presentation of computed data of student's evaluation, collected themes from in-depth interview, and the pedagogical model for flexible learning modality.

Table 1. *Performance Level of the Respondents in the content mastery of College Microbiology and Parasitology*

Content Area	Percentage (%)	Interpretation
General Morphology of Organism	39.67	Moderately Mastered
Infections and Host Resistance	39.25	Less Mastered
Microbial Controls	33.00	Less Mastered
Transmission and Pathogenesis	34.28	Less Mastered
Communicable diseases involving different organ systems	33.56	Less Mastered
Overall	35.48	Less Mastered

Table 2. *Performance Level of the Respondents in the cognitive skills of College Microbiology and Parasitology*

Content Area	Percentage (%)	Interpretation
Knowledge	31.78	Less Mastered
Comprehension	36.86	Less Mastered
Application	35.67	Less Mastered
Analysis	37.20	Less Mastered
Overall	34.93	Less Mastered

Table 3. *Summary Table for One-Way ANOVA for the Performance Level across content areas*

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	Interpretation	Decision
Between Groups	80	.	0.20	6.80	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Within Groups	.23	5	0.03				
Total	.03	9					

Note: P-value is < .000, which is less than 0.05 level of significance (alpha)

Table 4. Summary Table for Tukey's Honest Significant Difference (HSD) Test for the Performance Level across Content Areas

	Mean Difference	SE	t	Cohen's d	P _{Tukey}	
Gen. Morph.	H. Resistance	2.818	0.411	6.852	0.699 < .001	***
	M. Control	0.010	0.411	0.025	0.003 1.000	
	Pathogens	-2.615	0.411	-6.358	-0.649 < .001	***
	Com. disease	2.938	0.411	7.143	0.729 < .001	***
	Total	-20.661	0.411	-50.245	-5.128 < .001	***
H. Resist	M. Control	-2.807	0.411	-6.827	-0.697 < .001	***
	Pathogens	-5.432	0.411	-13.210	-1.348 < .001	***
	Com. disease	0.120	0.411	0.291	0.030 1.000	
	Total	-23.479	0.411	-57.097	-5.827 < .001	***
M. Control	Pathogens	-2.625	0.411	-6.383	-0.652 < .001	***
	Com. disease	2.927	0.411	7.118	0.726 < .001	***
	Total	-20.672	0.411	-50.270	-5.131 < .001	***
Pathogens	Com. disease	5.552	0.411	13.502	1.378 < .001	***
	Total	-18.047	0.411	-43.886	-4.479 < .001	***
Com. disease	Total	-23.599	0.411	-57.388	-5.857 < .001	***

Note. Cohen's d does not correct for multiple comparisons

Table 5. Summary Table for One-Way ANOVA for the Performance Level across cognitive skills

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	Interpretation	Decision
Between Groups	0.36	3	0.12	4.56	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
Within Groups	19.96	764	0.03				
Total	20.31	767					

Note: P-value is < .000, which is less than 0.05 level of significance (alpha)

Table 6. Summary Table for Tukey's Honest Significant Difference (HSD) Test for the Performance Level across cognitive skills

Box 4.1 Post Hoc Comparison – Cognitive Skills

	Mean Difference	SE	t	Cohen's d	P _{Tukey}	
Knowledge	Comprehension	-2.115	0.411	-5.142	-0.525 < .001	***
	Application	5.365	0.411	13.046	1.331 < .001	***
	Analysis	4.859	0.411	11.817	1.206 < .001	***
	Total	-17.62	0.411	-42.860	-4.374 < .001	***
Comprehension	Application	7.479	0.411	18.188	1.856 < .001	***
	Analysis	6.974	0.411	16.959	1.731 < .001	***
	Total	-15.510	0.411	-37.718	-3.850 < .001	***
Application	Analysis	-0.505	0.411	-1.229	-0.125 0.979	
	Total	-22.990	0.411	-55.906	-5.706 < .001	***
Analysis	Total	-22.484	0.411	-54.678	-5.581 < .001	***

Note. Cohen's d does not correct for multiple comparisons

Table 7. Themes on the student's experiences in online modality.

Clustered Themes	Emergent Themes
Experienced poor internet connection which affects their academic performance	Poor internet connection
Experienced financial instability	Financial instability
Out of focus due to home environment, family obligation and social media	Distraction
Low motivation and disappointment	Discouragement
Cannot explore due to unfamiliarity to the platforms	Unfamiliarity / lack of knowledge
Experienced headache due to online radiation	Mental stress
Provision of laboratory facility, equipment, equipment maintenance and supplies	Lack of school support
Provision of additional Science Master teachers	Lack of Master teachers
Monitoring and evaluation of teacher's teaching at school	Lack of teacher's monitoring and evaluation
Provision of unit subject extension	Lack of subject units
Provision of expert laboratory technician to maintain equipment	Lack of expert laboratory technician

Table 8. Themes on teacher’s experiences in online modality

Clustered Themes	Emergent Themes
Challenges experienced by the teachers in terms of teaching online	Challenges in Online – based teaching
Challenges experienced by the teachers in terms of laboratory monitoring performances of students	Challenges in Home- based experimentation
Challenges experienced by the teachers in terms of insufficient school laboratory equipment and supplies	Challenges in School – based experimentation
Challenges experienced of the teachers in improvising learning materials in Microbiology and Parasitology	Challenges in improvising Subject learning materials
Challenges in the delivery of subject’s concept among students	Misunderstanding and misconceptions among students
Challenges in introducing the significance or relevance of laboratory skills among students	Importance of laboratory skills
Need proper coordination for equipment and supplies request	Proper coordination between users and Laboratory-In charge

Table 9. Summary of the findings of sub-problems 1-5 in teaching and learning in online modality.

Student’s Evaluation	Teachers’ Experiences	Students’ Experiences
<p>The performance level of students in content mastery areas of college Microbiology and Parasitology have an overall mean score of 26.21 (35.48%) and was interpreted as a less mastered performance level. Specifically, Microbial control has a mean score of 5.94 (33.00%) which was interpreted as less mastered content area; Communicable diseases involving different organ systems means core was 3.02 (33.56%) and considered to be less mastered content area; Transmission and pathogenesis mean score was 8.57 (34.28%) and still less mastered content area; Infections and host resistance mean score was 3.14 (39.25%) and also interpreted as less mastered content area; and lastly, the General morphology of organisms mean score 5.95 (39.67%) was considered moderately mastered content area.</p>	Challenges in Online based teaching	Poor internet connection
	Challenges in Home-based experimentation	Financial instability
	Challenges in School – based experimentation	Distraction
	Challenges in improvising Subject learning materials	Discouragement
	Misunderstanding and misconceptions among students	Unfamiliarity / lack of knowledge
<p>The performance level of students in cognitive skills of college Microbiology and Parasitology have an overall mean score of 26.20 (34.93%) and was interpreted as a less mastered performance level. Specifically, Knowledge skill had a mean score of 8.58 (31.78%) was interpreted as less mastered skill; whereas the comprehension skill had a mean score of 10.69 (36.86%) and considered to be less mastered skill; Also, the application skill got mean score of 3.21 (35.67%) which was interpreted as less mastered skill, and lastly the analysis skill got the mean score of 3.72 (37.20 %). On one hand, there was a significant difference across all content areas and in cognitive skills of college Microbiology and Parasitology and hence Tukey HSD was established.</p>	Importance of laboratory skills	Mental stress
	Proper coordination between users and Laboratory-In charge	Lack of school support
		Lack of Master teachers
		Lack of teacher’s monitoring and evaluation
		Lack of subject units
	Lack of expert laboratory technician	

Discussion

Performance Level of the Respondents in the Content Areas

Results showed that the Microbial control content area got only 33.00 % among other content areas of the subject. This means that it

was considered to be the less mastered content area taken by the students. The General Morphology of Organism had the highest percentage score of 39.67. This means that the students had moderately mastered that content area among other content areas in the study. However, infectious and host resistance had almost the same percentage score of the General Morphology of Organism which got the second highest percentage of 39.25. In this content area students were evaluated to be less mastered. Similarly, Transmissions and Pathogenesis, and communicable disease involving different organ systems almost had the same percentage respectively 34.28 and 33.56. Thus, the overall performance level of the students in Microbiology and Parasitology was 35.48 % which can be interpreted as less mastered.

The data suggests that there is room for improvement in all content areas. The pedagogical approach used may not be fully effective, and adjustments or enhancements may be needed. Attention should be given to content areas with lower mean scores and percentages, such as Infections and Host Resistance and Communicable diseases involving different organ systems.

In schools, Teachers are often restricted in providing microbiological activities due to e.g. biosafety concerns, lack of resources, of confidence and of time. This was also found in a survey of UK school teachers (Abraham et al., 2015), preventing a third from offering practical microbiology. In addition, it was also supported by the study of Mutlu and Termiz (2013) that learning behind the screen is not an easy way of learning, especially for those taking Microbiology and Parasitology subjects because these subjects need laboratory classes. It's a hard time for them to fully adapt to new ways and understand the topics on their own. These findings implied that students should be thoroughly taught on microbial and parasitic understanding. This idea is supported by Liu et al. (2018) that the understanding in the pathogenesis due to bacteria and parasites's control and prevention should be highlighted in science education.

Performance level of the students in the cognitive skills

In the study, it was depicted that the respondent's knowledge got the percentage score was 31.78 and hence it can be interpreted that they have less mastery in their cognitive skills. Similarly, in comprehension, they had a percentage score of 36.86. This can be interpreted that students have also less mastered in comprehension skill whereas the respondent's application skill was 35.67% which means that in this skill was less mastered. Lastly, the respondents in the analysis percentage score was 37.20 which means that their analysis skills were also less mastered as the results showed and interpreted in the study. The overall cognitive skills performance across knowledge, comprehension, application, and analysis is less mastered, with an overall mean percentage of 34.93%.

The data suggests a consistent pattern of less mastery across various cognitive skills. There may be challenges in the instructional methods or assessments used for these cognitive skill areas. The overall performance is slightly below the threshold for a moderate level of mastery. Hence, there is a need for focused intervention and instructional adjustments to improve the overall mastery of cognitive skills among the learners.

Cognitive skills development is among important college student outcomes given its "applicability and utility across a wide range of different content areas. Colaco (2017) suggests that science process skills are needed to improve cognitive skills towards the subject, particularly engaging students in activities that are likely to heighten the students' interest and abilities. However, teachers in higher education are faced with the challenge of engaging their students as surmised.

As opined by Hew (2016), engaging students in the online learning environment is often more challenging than in traditional face-to-face courses. In fact, from the in-depth interview of the researcher, the student's engagement was hindered by poor internet connection. Thus, they cannot fully participate in online discussion. For instance, below are the exact lines or statements that were drawn from the in-depth interview and translated into English, Interviewee 1: "Maka stress gyud siya sir example gud sir during quiz bigla nalang mawala ang connection... (It was really stressful sir, for instance during the quiz immediately loss of connection) [P 169, L 102-103]. Interviewee 2: "Internet hehehehe....hinay man gud sya minsan sir. Di na maintindihan ang sinasabi ng teacher.... (The internet (hehehehe), slow connection. Cannot understand what's our teacher say all about) [P 169, L109-110]

Another theme or factor that deeply affects them learning Microbiology and Parasitology online is the home-based laboratory integration where their practical skills to handle laboratory analysis such as microbial analysis and parasitic analysis were affected. This was supported during the interview that most of them experienced difficulty when it comes to experiment due to lack of school support. For instance, "Minsan sir kapag kulang ang chemicals hindi na kami magproceed. Doon nalang sa next na topic na available yong chemicals... (Sometimes sir if the reagents are not available then we will not conduct laboratories. If available then we will proceed the next day...) [P 172, L253-254]. The impact of the integration of home-based laboratories according to the study of Almahasees et. al (2021) that 11% of the given home activities did not contribute to respondent's understanding and while 27% of the respondents stated the activities were not significant for the topic. Therefore, although the addition of in-house experiments provide a complementary tool for understanding the main concepts in biochemistry along with improving skills in scientific thinking, this should be accompanied by a good feedback mechanism from the instructors. This is observed by Nadia et al. (2017) that the students felt significantly more confident and comfortable operating laboratory equipment, but they did not feel more motivated to engage in virtual laboratories compared to real laboratories.

Significant difference in the performance level of the respondents across the different content areas

Looking at the results of the statistics of problem 1, the test of difference between performance levels among respondents across content

areas. The null hypothesis (H_0) suggests that there is no significant difference between performance levels of respondents across content areas. The analysis of variance indicates a significant difference in

performance levels among respondents across content areas. The p-value is less than the chosen level of significance (α), which is typically set at 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected. This means that there is at least one performance level on the content area that is different from the other performance level of the respondents on the content area. The significant difference between performance levels across content areas suggests that there are variations in how well respondents performed in different areas of the study.

Furthermore, table 4 data presentation, shows that the performance level of students across the content mastery areas is significantly different, then a post-hoc test utilizing Tukey HSD was performed to identify which is really different among the performance levels of the respondents across the content areas. The post hoc Tukey HSD test results provide the mean differences between different content areas in terms of performance levels.

The mean difference between General Morphology and Host Resistance is significant ($p < .001$). The positive mean difference suggests that General Morphology has a higher mean score compared to Host Resistance. The effect size (Cohen's d) of 0.699 indicates a moderate effect.

The mean difference between General Morphology and Microbial Control is not significant ($p = 1.000$). The p-value is greater than the significance level, suggesting no statistically significant difference between these two content areas. The mean difference between General Morphology and Pathogens is significant ($p < .001$). The negative mean difference indicates that Pathogens has a higher mean score compared to General Morphology. The effect size (Cohen's d) of -0.649 indicates a moderate effect.

The mean difference between General Morphology and Communicable Disease is significant ($p < .001$). The positive mean difference suggests that General Morphology has a higher mean score compared to Communicable Disease. The effect size (Cohen's d) of 0.729 indicates a moderate effect. The overall total mean difference is highly significant ($p < .001$), indicating that there are significant differences in the mean scores across all content areas. The large negative mean difference and Cohen's d suggest a significant difference in performance levels.

The mean difference between Host Resistance and Microbial Control is significant ($p < .001$). The negative mean difference indicates that Host Resistance has a higher mean score compared to Microbial Control. The effect size (Cohen's d) of -0.697 suggests a moderate effect. The mean difference between Host Resistance and Pathogens is highly significant ($p < .001$). The negative mean difference indicates that Host Resistance has a higher mean score compared to Pathogens. The effect size (Cohen's d) of -1.348 suggests a large effect.

The mean difference between Host Resistance and Communicable Disease is not significant ($p = 1.000$). The p-value is greater than the significance level, suggesting no statistically significant difference between these two content areas. The overall total mean difference is highly significant ($p < .001$), indicating that there are significant differences in the mean scores across all content areas. The large negative mean difference and Cohen's d suggest a significant difference in performance levels. The mean difference between Pathogens and Communicable Disease is significant ($p < .001$). The negative mean difference indicates that Pathogens has a lower mean score compared to Communicable Disease. The effect size (Cohen's d) of -0.652 suggests a moderate effect. The overall total mean difference is highly significant ($p < .001$), indicating that there are significant differences in the mean scores across all content areas. The large negative mean difference and Cohen's d suggest a significant difference in performance levels.

General Morphology shows significant differences in mean scores when compared to Host Resistance, Pathogens, and Communicable Disease. Microbial Control does not exhibit significant differences in mean scores when compared to other content areas. The overall total result suggests a significant overall difference in performance levels across all content areas. Host Resistance shows significant differences in mean scores when compared to Microbial Control and Pathogens. Communicable Disease does not exhibit significant differences in mean scores when compared to other content areas.

The overall total result suggests a significant overall difference in performance levels across all content areas. Pathogens show a significant difference in mean scores compared to Communicable Disease. The overall total result suggests a significant overall difference in performance levels across all content areas.

Significant difference in the performance level of the respondents across the different cognitive skills

Looking at the results of the statistics of problem 2, the results of an analysis aimed at determining whether there is a significant difference in performance levels among respondents across different cognitive skills. The null hypothesis (H_0) suggests that there is no significant difference in performance levels among respondents across different cognitive skills. While the alternative hypothesis (H_a) posits that there is a significant difference in performance levels among respondents across different cognitive skills. The analysis indicates a significant difference in performance levels among respondents across cognitive skills.

The p-value is less than the chosen level of significance (α), which is set at 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted. The significant difference between performance levels across cognitive skills suggests

that there are variations in how well respondents performed in different cognitive skill areas. The null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, indicating that the differences observed are unlikely due to random chance. This means that at least one performance level among respondents across different cognitive skills is different from the other.

Furthermore, based on table 5 data presentation, provides a detailed comparison of mean differences between different cognitive skills, helping to identify which skills are significantly different from each other in terms of performance levels. The mean difference between Knowledge and Comprehension is significant ($p < .001$). The negative mean difference indicates that Knowledge has a lower mean score compared to Comprehension. The effect size (Cohen's d) of -0.525 suggests a moderate effect. The mean difference between Knowledge and Application is highly significant ($p < .001$). The positive mean difference indicates that Knowledge has a higher mean score compared to Application. The effect size (Cohen's d) of 1.331 suggests a large effect. The mean difference between Knowledge and Analysis is highly significant ($p < .001$). The positive mean difference indicates that Knowledge has a higher mean score compared to Analysis. The effect size (Cohen's d) of 1.206 suggests a large effect.

The mean differences between total and each cognitive skill (Knowledge, Comprehension, Application, and Analysis) are highly significant ($p < .001$). The negative mean differences indicate that total has lower mean scores compared to each individual cognitive skill. The large negative Cohen's d values suggest significant differences in performance levels. The findings reveal that Comprehension, Application, and Analysis show significant differences in mean scores compared to Knowledge. Total (combined cognitive skills) has significantly lower mean scores compared to each individual cognitive skill (Knowledge, Comprehension, Application, and Analysis). The large mean differences between total and individual cognitive skills suggest that the combination of skills may be more challenging for respondents.

Experiences of Teachers in Flexible Content Delivery

Results from the thorough interview on teacher's experiences in teaching college Microbiology and Parasitology under flexible learning modality are the Challenges in Online – based teaching, Challenges in Home- based experimentation, Challenges in School – based experimentation, Challenges in improvising Subject learning materials, Misunderstanding and misconceptions among students, Importance of laboratory skills, and Proper coordination between users and Laboratory-In charge.

For the challenges experienced by the Teachers and Students in flexible learning delivery, they experienced online teaching preparation, readiness, and application of technology – based approach. Specifically, preparation in school tasks. Despite this event, they made strategies like attending seminars to be used during online modality. Other challenges are teachers unable to monitor students due to internet connection and therefore, teachers need an extra effort to ensure students' attendance online. In Challenges experienced in Home- based experimentation, due to limited access in school physical contact, home – based experimentation was applied in colleges and universities. This is evident when Key Informants said that they also conducted home – based experiments in Flexible Learning Modality but they have become considerate in giving grades due to online modality since they cannot monitor the microbial and parasitic analysis skills of students. According to Nadia et al. (2017) about comparison between virtual and real laboratory integration results showed that after completing virtual laboratory cases, the students felt significantly more confident and comfortable operating laboratory equipment, but they did not feel more motivated to engage in virtual laboratories compared to real laboratories. Kenengsih (2017) said that practical activities in the microbiology course must be carried out in the laboratory.

For challenges experienced in School – based experimentation they have challenges experienced in their own school laboratories such as uncondusive because no proper ventilation, incomplete reagents, equipment and apparatus such as reagents, and microscopes can compromise the skills of students or the laboratory performance of the teacher and student. A conducive school laboratory should have sufficient supplies and equipment plus a well-ventilated or air-conditioned facility. As mentioned by Kenengsih (2017) that practical activities in the microbiology course must be carried out in the laboratory. If in case there is insufficiency in school laboratory and equipment, the target objectives of the course cannot be achieved. Furthermore, they have challenges experienced in improvising Subject learning materials, since pandemic; usually the discussion is through online presentation using different platforms like google meet, zoom, or Moodle. Thus, teachers shifted from books or modules into an online – based approach by making different presentations like the powerpoint presentations. It is quite challenging for those teachers who have low technology or computer literacy. Therefore, they should undergo training and orientations on how to use computers and specific platforms offered by their respective schools. According to the key informants, they have no option but to improvise learning materials of Microbiology and related topics in order to assist the needs of their students. This is their way to meet up the required skills in the laboratory. Misunderstanding and misconceptions among students also experienced by the teachers in Flexible Learning Modality. Byrne (2011) and Kurt (2013) said that several studies showed students at each education level have different misconceptions about microbes. From this observation, how much more if the students are learning in flexible modality. In the present study, the misunderstanding and misconceptions in science particularly in Microbiology and Parasitology content areas are among the challenges faced by teachers under flexible learning modality. Note that misconceptions are crucial in the cognitive skills of the students. As teachers, it is their role to introduce the concepts of each content area so that the comprehension, analysis, application, and knowledge skills of the students will be improved. There are several factors that can influence the misunderstanding and misconceptions of the students.

According to the Key informants of the study, these two are “evidently experienced” by their students in an online modality. This means that they would prefer the traditional classes because they can actually monitor and evaluate

the academic performances of their students in terms across the Microbiology and Parasitology content area. This experience is related to the study conducted by Cardona et al. (2022) on teacher's perspective in science in flexible learning modality showed that the communication barriers and the integrity of student assessment were among the issues that science teachers faced because flexible learning is new to our educational system. This implies that if teachers had experienced these, then there is a high tendency that students can also experience misunderstandings that could lead to misconceptions in the subject.

Additionally, Teachers also significantly affected or challenged the importance of laboratory skills in flexible delivery. The role of laboratory activity to the cognitive skills of the students is very significant. The concepts of the content areas in Microbiology and Parasitology are better understood when there is an application of hands-on experimentation. Key Informants or teachers believed that laboratory skills only achieved when there is support from school administrators on the provisions of the insufficiency of supplies and equipment in the laboratory. As cited in the study of Bindayna (2020) that the laboratory sessions provide students an opportunity to revisit the subject under study in another platform through observation, identification, and interpretation. Lastly, they are also experienced in dealing with the Laboratory-In charge. Aside from enough supplies of reagents and equipment, Laboratory personnel are very important in the school system. The laboratory supplies and equipment requests are the function of the Laboratory – In charge. Therefore, users should request reagents and equipment to the laboratory office. However, if still unsupported by the school administrator, problems of reagents and equipment insufficiency will remain and thus laboratory performances are continued.

Experiences of Students in studying in Flexible Online Modality

Selected students from the different Tertiary Educational Institutions (TEIs) in Region 12 were interviewed concerning their experiences under the flexible learning modality in College Microbiology and Parasitology. Through Focus Group Discussion (FGD), the researcher obtained significant data from the group of students of each selected TEI. Prior the FGD method, the researcher sought approval from school authorities then informing each respective dean of the College of Teacher Education (CTE) on the research's interview protocol including its objectives, possible probing questions, and the role of their students in the study then followed by sending an invitation to all target respondents. An informed consent was also given to them a day before the actual interview.

The researcher followed the ethical considerations in the study. Thus, only those students who signed the informed consent were included in the FGD. Before the actual interview, the researcher discussed the interview rules, specifically the audio recording protocol and its main purpose were thoroughly discussed by the researcher to the respondents and once settled, then the actual interview followed. In general, respondents were asked about their experiences encountered under flexible learning modality. These experiences are potential factors to a student's mastery in content areas and cognitive skills in College Microbiology and Parasitology under the flexible learning modality. In the analysis of the interview on students' experiences, the results showed that poor internet connection, financial instability, distraction, discouragement, unfamiliarity or lack of knowledge, mental stress, lack of school support, lack of master's teachers, lack of teacher's monitoring and evaluation, lack of subject units, and lack of expert laboratory technician.

For the poor internet connection as experienced by the Students, during the pandemic, the entire Tertiary Educational Institutions (TEIs) shifted traditional face to face education into flexible learning modality. Therefore, home-based learning was applied in order to sustain the education of the entire States, Universities, and Colleges (SUCs) in the Philippines. In region 12, the Commission of Higher Education or CHED mandated local SUCs to adapt face to face and virtual learning modality or flexible learning modality to ensure the continuation of the educational system. However, the internet is the only means for students to be able to attend virtual classes. Therefore, the use of the internet became rampant. Accordingly, students experienced poor internet connection and also limited internet access in school. Poor internet connection affected or compromised their "online task submissions like quiz", "academic performance as shown in their scores or ratings", "caused stress", and "teacher discussion" was also affected. There was also limited access to the internet in school. Through school provided the internet but according to them not all areas or school buildings have internet access. According to Barrera et al. (2020) that online solutions carry some disadvantages for student learning, including technical problems such as a poor internet connection. This led to students who were not actively involved.

Financial instability is among the experiences of the students due to COVID-19. Some students experienced financial instability due to the pandemic period. People are jobless or have irregular workloads that clearly affect their income and hence extra expenses beyond the basic needs in the family are a big deal. In the interview, some of them said that "gadgets are very important in online classes but not all students have the financial capability to buy android phones or smartphones". This financial instability was significantly affected by the COVID-19. According to Basialia et al. (2020) that the socio – economy of the entire world has been affected by the pandemic crisis. In the present study investigation, some of the students' academic endeavors are restricted due to incapacity to use mobile application in flexible learning modality. They were also unable to access educational materials, radio learning, informative television, and online educational resources since they could not attend school (Bergdahl, 2021).

Academic Distraction is evident in Flexible Learning Difficulty. A lot of challenges were experienced by most of them during flexible learning modality such as their own "parents", "household chores", "social media (games and facebook)", and "pets at home". According to them, their parents are used to ordering "household chores such as cooking" during their classes online. Social media like the games and facebook are two distractors of their online studies. They are out of focus in paying attention to their classes. Domestic animals or pets at home also distract them because of the noisy environment they created. In their experience of being discouraged, Students experienced low motivation and disappointment during online modality. Distant peers and teachers' communication might be

the reasons for experiencing low motivation. Thus, those people who are low motivated are prone to disappointment in life. Physical communication increases self-confidence and enthusiasm. In school, students are actively engaged with their classmates (peers) and teachers and hence they would be highly motivated due to the normal environment they are in. This is observed in the study conducted by Lazaga and Madrigal (2021) that online learning makes students lazy, lacking motivation to learn due to lack of internet connection, confusion, and adjustment to the online platform modality. Moreover, unfamiliarity or lack of knowledge is also evident to them, the use of technology became rampant in schools and likewise the use of different platforms is needed in order to adopt technology-based learning. In the interview, some of the respondents experienced difficulty in exploring the platforms introduced to them by their teachers. They are unfamiliar on how to operate the system of the platforms such as Moodle and zoom. These experiences can be traced from the observation of Geng (2019) that when students are aware of the use of tools and platforms for learning, as well as student's technology readiness then learning can be delivered effectively. On one hand, mental stress is caused by distant learning as Students perceive it online. Interviewed students experienced mental stress because of online - based learning. Accordingly, they experienced headaches due to radiation as they were exposed to computers. Another source of stress would be internet connection. Unsubmitted quizzes online made them stressful because it would affect their academic ratings or scores. According to Cicha (2021) and Rangel – Perez (2021) that the influence of COVID - 19 is only ICTs integration, and student's workload (Crawford, 2020) but also to the welfare of all parties involved in the process, e.g., psychological pressure or sense of isolation (Bozkurt, 2020).

Another significant experience is the lack of school support. Better education lies from the support of the school by providing the needs of the specific program / college in terms of facilities, school supplies, and equipment. In science programs, insufficient equipment and supplies could be crucial to the cognitive skills of students because hands-on experiments must be experienced in the laboratory. According to the interviewed respondents, their schools have lack of support in the laboratory supplies (Chemicals and other reagents) and some important equipment (Microscopes). Some of them said that reagents are requested by the laboratory - in charge but most of the time no feedback from school and hence they are forced to provide using their own money which is not right. Further, others said that if the reagents or chemicals are not available in the laboratory, they are forced to skip the activity or no longer perform the activity. Moreover, the facility is not only meant for science education because interviewed respondents said that BS nursing, and other science courses also use their facility. Another interviewed student said that aircon and ventilation are lacking in their school laboratories. Facility is very humid and uncomfortable. Therefore, the use of equipment such as microscopes is limited. Thus, they wanted more additional microscopes in their schools.

Moreover, the lack of school support in the current study was also observed by Iqbal (2022) in his study that the schools in the Pakistani Higher Education Institution had experienced the same problem. In addition to this, lack of Master's Teachers is seen by the Students in their respective schools. In the interview, most of the respondents said that their teachers are all masters teachers by profession but teaching them the science subjects which are not their field of specialization. Others said that teachers, when asked questions, only provide a very shallow explanation. It seems like they are expecting more answers. Thus, they would want that their teachers in science are all masters teachers with a field or subject area of specialization. According to Migalang et al (2018) in order to address the poor achievement in Science and to attain the goals of science education, teaching strategy should be developed for science teachers in order to achieve meaningful and retentive learning. Students also said that lack of Teacher's Monitoring and Evaluation is a must.

Teacher's monitoring and evaluation is normally conducted by the school administrator in order to sustain the academic endeavors and commitment in school work. In the interview, respondents said that their schools lack of teacher's monitoring and evaluation. Further, they said that their teachers should be monitored in school while teaching them because they experienced classes for a short period of time since their teachers come late and out early in their classes. According to them, their learning is compromised because there is no proper and enough time should be spent in the discussion. They cannot further ask questions because of this situation. One of the interviewees said that the teacher seemed to be using her/his freedom or standard of teaching and so they could not complain about it. Others complained that the evaluation should be conducted face to face instead of online. Therefore, most of them requested actual teacher's monitoring and evaluation instead of online evaluation. Lack of subject units is also experienced at school. Interviewed students said that the units in the laboratory should be increased because the laboratory requires more time than lecture based on their experience. Accordingly, it is difficult for them to finish one experiment in a short period of time because the activity varies from time to time. Thus, they would want the subject units, particularly subjects with laboratories to be changed.

Lastly, Students experienced the lack of expert laboratory technicians. An office requires personnel for operations like a science laboratory to cater the needs of the students and teachers at school. Lack of laboratory technician or expert in handling laboratories are commonly observed by the participants. Based on their experience, the maintenance in the laboratory equipment is not regularly checked and they might be afraid that this would affect their laboratory performance. One of the interviewees from one college said that Microscope is very dirty. They cannot properly use the lenses of the microscope because some dust appeared in the lenses. Another student said there is equipment available in the laboratory but not allowed to be utilized and it made him wonder why. Another interviewee said that the space of the facility is very small and very humid. Lack of ventilation and so on. Hence, they would want an expert laboratory technician to assist their needs during the experiment.

A Pedagogical Model for Microbiology and Parasitology in Science Education

Introduction

To achieve a highest performance level in the cognitive skills in microbiology and parasitology students need to have deeper understanding on its content mastery areas. To achieve this, students must be engaged in the practical activities aside from conceptual-based learning or theory-based learning. However, teachers were challenged with the impact of online modality. These challenges were observed in many higher educations that teachers had experienced difficulty on how to engage their students in online modality (Colaco, 2017). This suggests that teacher's pedagogy needs to be enhanced in order that they can effectively deliver the flexible content. Therefore, unchanged instructional strategies used during traditional classes might not be effective anymore to the overall performance of students in Microbiology and Parasitology. Hence, science teachers should utilize technology to deliver science curriculum, assess learners, direct them to research topics, and to use student-centered strategies integrated with technology. Thus, in this current study, the researcher designed the MERick's Pedagogical Model to enhance the pedagogy in College Microbiology and Parasitology under flexible learning modality. Enhancement of pedagogy will improve the student's cognitive skills.

Rationale

This model was derived from the actual evaluation on the performance levels of content mastery areas and cognitive skills of the 192 BSED – Science Students in selected Tertiary Education Institutions (TEIs) in region 12. In support of the outcome of the evaluation, an in-depth interview was also administered to those students who showed willingness to be interviewed on experiences under flexible learning modality. Findings from the performance evaluation and in-depth interview were used as instruments and came up with the MERick model for online teaching and learning purposes. It aimed to enhance flexible content and learning delivery in Microbiology and Parasitology.

Goals and Objectives

The goal of the model is to enhance the Teacher's Pedagogy and Student's performance level in College Microbiology and Parasitology in selected Tertiary Education Institutions with BSED - Science Education in Region 12. To achieve this goal it needs specific objectives which are anchored from main components of the designed model that showed interrelationships with each other such as teacher the one who delivers the flexible teaching, Student who is the recipient of teacher's pedagogy or experienced the flexible learning, Flexible Learning Modality Experiences, and Key Areas for Improvement.

Guiding principles

With the findings perceived from the respondent's evaluation, FGD, and KII in the selected participants, this resulted in a proposal for a pedagogical model in Microbiology and Parasitology in Flexible Learning Modality based on the following principles: quality and learning experience; ethics and academic integrity; digital inclusion and accessibility; open science and environmental sustainability; flexibility; and interaction. The model will be validated by e-Learning and pedagogical experts before it can be implemented as a model in the TEIs.

Framework of MERick's Pedagogical Model

Figure 1. MERick's Pedagogical Model

As illustrated in figure 1, there are two individuals who played vital and distinct roles in science education. One is the student, who is the recipient of all the knowledge from the content mastery areas of the subject. The student's cognitive skills depend on how she or he acquires or understands those contents or concepts in Microbiology and Parasitology. If students got less mastery or least mastery performance level in all the content areas then their cognitive skills are also the same level. The two variables content mastery and cognitive skill need more attention in school. To become highly performing students, they need to understand the broad and interconnected concepts of Microbiology and Parasitology such as General Morphology of Organisms, Infections and Host Resistance, Microbial Controls, Transmission and Pathogenesis; and Communicable diseases involving different organ systems. But in the study, findings revealed that the overall performance level of students in those content areas was interpreted as less mastery with a mean score of 26.21 (35.48%). Therefore, predictably, the cognitive performance level was also less mastery with a mean score of 26.20 (34.93%).

As mentioned during the interview to some of the respondents, the internet was one of the reasons or themes they considered that affect much of their online participation or engagement. Lines stated during the interrogations were, "Di ka mag-anu mag connect (cannot connect) [P167, L24], "Makaffect sa amoang academic performance...(Can affect our academic performance) [P169, L100], "Maka stress gyud siya sir example gud sir during quiz bigla nalang mawala ang connection...(It was really stressful sir, for instance during quiz immediately loss of connection) [P169, L 102-103], Internet hehehehe....hinay man gud sya minsan sir. Di na maintindihan ang sinasabi ng teacher.... (The internet (hehehehe), slow connection. Cannot understand what our teacher says all about) [P169, L109-110]."

Another significant person who is involved in the model is the teacher. They play the most important role since she or he is the one who delivers the flexible content among his or her students. Although students can learn on their own, the proper education starts by proper guidance of teachers and thus school is the best venue for proper education.

However, as mentioned by them during the in-depth interview, they faced challenges in flexible content delivery due to some factors or themes. For instance, "Sir in handling laboratory sir, especially nowadays we're online it is very difficult to give instructions or if they really follow the procedures properly [P164,L80-81], "Sir it was quite challenging because I used to teach my students in a traditional way. There's a huge difference when it comes to teaching the subject like how you handle the students online where in fact, they are many students [P162, L16-18], and "I experienced difficulty to reach them online because of poor internet connection [P163, L51-52]." Teachers described that giving instructions in a home-based laboratory was very hard. This means it could lead to misunderstanding or misconceptions. This was mentioned by one of the key informants that, "Sadly, misunderstanding, misconceptions like you showed a video in return they will make the activity on record then they will return to me so there is really a communication barrier. you are thinking it is alright but to them not.. Actually there are few students that really do not know how to follow... [P165, L118-121]. This was one of the dilemmas where professional teachers had to go through due to online modality. Flexible content delivery was hindered by poor internet connection and other themes. Based on some enumerated experiences mentioned by the teachers and students, the MERick model placed key areas for improvement. Though teachers had flexible content delivery they showed commitment and passion in their professions. This was shown during online modality.

As mentioned during the interview that teachers had to improvise methods using alternative materials just to augment lessons online such as, "I need to look ways sir because students need to learn the skills in microbiology and parasitology... [P165, L122-123], "Sir since the Pandemic Microbiology and Parasitology I only improvised materials since students cannot go to school so I just gave them what materials they should use. In terms of the experiment, I cannot follow what is in the manual since for sure no materials at home can determine."

The key areas for improvements could be supported by the stakeholders, school administrators, and the local government units or LGU by only the teachers. There must be a collaborative effort to sustain better and high quality science education. Future workforces from this sector would potentially become scientists or researchers not only in education but in allied courses. Significantly, school administrators should provide more opportunities between the teachers and students based on the experiences under flexible learning modality. The school can send professionals to webinars and trainings related to how teachers integrate technology in their lectures using educational online games like Kahoot. Teachers who have a lack of knowledge on how to use technology cannot provide conducive and remarkable teaching.

On one hand, schools must provide synchronous and asynchronous programs so that learners can adjust and prepare for online tasks submission. Also, reduce expenses of loads, and free from burdens in attending class online due to poor internet connections. It must be considered that the school should reduce laboratory fees and other miscellaneous fees because students are not full time attending and using electricity and facilities in school. During the interview, students had to provide reagents and equipment and some of these reasons were divulged by some of the students, "Ako sir masuggest nako sir is given na ang meron kami facility peru may mga equipment na kulang like kami pa nagapalit heheheheh kasi dli sya available sa laboratory sir...(For me sir is that though we have facility but there is insufficient equipment and hence we had to buy since requested equipment is not available...) [P171, L 209-210], "I suggest sir na e raise nato ang concern sa department sir kay lain pod siya sa part sa students sir nga gabayad sila og tuition sir nga dapat....nga gabayad ka og laboratory fee pag abot sa actual laboratory walay mga gamit tapos student pa ang magprovide which is wrong. Hassle siya sa part nako sir sa isa ka tao or estudyante... (I suggest sir to raise this concern to the department because it is not okay that us sir students pay the tuition including laboratory fees then during the laboratory activity there is no equipment that forces

us to buy the equipment which is wrong and hassle on our part as a human and as a student...) [P171, L 212-214].”

Conclusion

In the light of the findings of study, conclusions were derived with respect to all the problems in the study: The learners have a moderate level of mastery in the General Morphology of Organism content area. Similar to Infections and Host Resistance, Microbial Controls, transmissions and pathogenesis, and communicable diseases involving different organ systems show a less mastered level. Therefore, the overall performance level of the students across the content areas is less mastered.

The overall cognitive skills performance across knowledge, comprehension, application, and analysis is less mastered, with an overall mean percentage of 34.93% because the data suggests a consistent pattern of less mastery across various cognitive skills.

The analysis of variance indicates a significant difference in performance levels among respondents across content areas because there is at least one performance level on the content area that is different from the other performance level of the respondents on the content area. Hence, it can be concluded that there was a significant difference across content master areas.

The analysis indicates a significant difference in performance levels among respondents across cognitive skills because there is that at least one performance level among respondents across different cognitive skills is different from the other. Hence, it can be concluded that there was a significant difference across content master areas.

It can be concluded that teachers and students experienced flexible content and learning delivery in online modality. The performance level in content mastery and cognitive skills are proof of its impact among the respondents.

Based on the findings from the entire evaluation in the performance of the students, and from an in-depth interview, the researcher concluded that the pedagogy needs to be enhanced using appropriate online platform learning models. The MERick Pedagogical Model was introduced to enhance teacher’s pedagogy and student’s engagement in online modality in College Microbiology and Parasitology.

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